

Conference Abstract

Regolith Weathering, Plastic Deformation and Hydrologic Evolution in a Volcanic Landscape

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Abstract

Landscape level observations of streams on the island of Hawai'i indicate that runoff ratios are essentially zero on the young active volcanic surfaces of windward Mauna Loa and Kilauea volcanoes and increase with age on the older Mauna Kea and Kohala surfaces. Recent work on both permanent and ephemeral stream flows shows that the changes in runoff are associated with decreases in saturated hydraulic conductivity (k_h) and aquifer thickness (D) that change with surface age (Perez-Fodich et al. 2024). The processes that control k in soils are plausibly related to weathering but the mechanisms are complex. Chemical weathering causes mass loss and most weathering reactions have negative ΔV so intuitively weathering should increase porosity (f) and likely k_h . Dry bulk density r_s of weathered soils initially does decrease with weathering mass losses. However trends in r_s reverse with further age, and calculated soil strain becomes negative. A model of poro-plastic deformation where the medium comprises an incompressible matrix with a finite yield stress and a void fraction f that is deformable but has zero yield stress (e.g. Gurson (1977)) can represent the evolution of soil strain if is a function of weathering mass loss. In this model the overall plastic yield limit is a function of both k and f . The constitutive relation between chemical alteration and strength of the residual soil matrix is not known in detail. I hypothesize that the yield stress of the residual matrix is a function of the loss of network-forming components such as SiO_2 , and that the change in yield stress can be described with a power law function of an alteration and mass loss index such as enrichment in an immobile element Nb/Nb_0 . The resulting

change in soil hydraulic properties diminishes vertical infiltration and promotes lateral flow toward incipient streams. The resulting incision leads to marked landscape level changes in hydrology and geomorphology, enhanced by incising stream capture of groundwater in shallow aquifers.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Gurson AL (1977) Continuum Theory of Ductile Rupture by Void Nucleation and Growth: Part I—Yield Criteria and Flow Rules for Porous Ductile Media. *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology* 99 (1): 2-15. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3443401>
- Perez-Fodich A, Derry L, Marçais J, Walter MT (2024) The effect of weathering in runoff-to-groundwater partitioning in the Island of Hawai'i: Perspectives for landscape evolution. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 635 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2024.118687>